

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Comparative Analysis of Deep Learning Methods for Classification of Ablated Regions in Hyperspectral Images of Atrial Tissue

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ABSTRACT Radiofrequency ablation (RFA) is used to treat atrial fibrillation (AF). Viability gaps between ablated regions can lead to AF recurrence; thus, correctly detecting RFA lesions is important for successful treatment. Hyperspectral imaging (HSI) has been previously shown to aid in visualizing RFA-affected areas. However, automated classification of ablated/unablated tissue in HSI remains open. We comparatively analyze state-of-the-art deep learning models for HSI classification from the field of remote sensing. We group them based on model architecture and utilization of spectral and spatial contexts. We deploy a pre-clinical HSI dataset obtained from excised left atrial tissue of four porcine and five bovine samples. The 45 classification algorithms are benchmarked through two types of experiments: objective and subjective. For objective evaluation, per HSI cube, we limit the training and testing to rectangular areas of known classes (ablated/unablated), as reliable classification masks for whole HSI cubes are not available. For both porcine and bovine data, models incorporating graph neural networks demonstrate superior performance. The best eight algorithms are further compared in a subjective experiment. We ask seventeen participants to rate RGB visualizations of model outputs. In this experiment, the performance of an algorithm is assessed on the whole HSI cube, and is subject to participants' interpretation of the extent of RFA-affected tissue. Our comparative analysis allows us to observe the suitability of different deep learning architectures for HSI classification of affected tissue. These efforts contribute towards the potential future utilization of HSI for surgical guidance in RFA or similar procedures.

INDEX TERMS Atrial tissue ablation, comparative analysis, convolutional neural networks, deep learning, graph neural networks, hyperspectral image classification, survey, transformer networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Hyperspectral imaging captures information from across a portion of the electromagnetic spectrum. Per spatial pixel in an image scene, a hyperspectral imager typically records the signal across dozens or hundreds of wavelengths, thus approximating the continuous spectrum. In contrast,

traditional color images collect the signal from typically three or four discrete channels. For instance, RGB images have three color channels per pixel. Thus, unlike color images forming a 2D image with three–four channels, a hyperspectral image (HSI) is a 3D structure, called a *hyperspectral cube* with two spatial, x and y , and one spectral, λ , axes.

This difference in structure implies that hyperspectral images are larger and more informative than color images, leading to active HSI utilization in various fields [1], ranging

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from agriculture [2] to archaeology [3] to biomedical tissue analysis [4]. Hyperspectral imaging has recently been utilized for the inspection of radiofrequency (RF) ablated regions on heart atrial tissue [5], [6], [7]. This is motivated by the potential of HSI to reveal the extent of tissue damage during surgical RF ablation interventions because accurate estimation of RF ablation impact may be used for surgical guidance to reduce the risk of atrial fibrillation (AF) recurrence [5].

To follow up the work of [5], [6], and [7], we focus on the task of *automated classification* of intact and RF ablated regions in pre-clinical HSI of atrial tissue using deep learning (DL). Our dataset includes autofluorescence HSI of several excised porcine and bovine left atrial tissue samples. To the best of our knowledge, this specific clinical application has not been considered for DL analysis before.

However, the task of automated HSI classification has been widely explored in the context of remote sensing, and various deep learning architectures have been proposed and evaluated on established aerial datasets. Thus, our main objective is to identify which DL architectures for HSI classification are best suited for our biomedical tissue analysis application. We perform an extensive comparative analysis of 1) different DL architecture types, and 2) combinations of HSI cube axes utilized for information propagation (spatial only, spectral only, or both) to achieve the most promising classification results. Additionally, we look into algorithm performance changes between the porcine and the bovine datasets. We base our conclusions on both numerical comparisons of the different algorithms in a specifically designed classification setting, and subjective evaluation of algorithm performance by multiple human raters.

We briefly review automated analysis of HSI in biomedical applications in Section II. Section III presents an overview and discussion of the state-of-the-art deep learning approaches for HSI classification. We describe the pre-clinical HSI dataset of radiofrequency ablated porcine and bovine atrial tissue in Section IV. Our objective quantitative benchmarking experiments and their results for the 45 considered approaches can be found in Section V. Section VI presents follow-up experimental comparisons based on subjective evaluation of classification algorithm performance by human raters. Section VII concludes the article and outlines potential directions for future work.

II. BIOMEDICAL HYPERSPECTRAL IMAGING

The application of HSI in the biomedical field is expanding rapidly, spanning areas such as cancer detection [4], [8], [9], [10], [11], classification of blood cells [12], [13], and semantic organ segmentation [14]. Detailed reviews of the usage of HSI in biomedical applications can be found in [15], [16], [17], [18], [19], and [20].

Both classical machine learning (ML) and deep learning approaches have been employed to address biomedical HSI (BHSI) classification. Fabelo et al. [4] propose a hybrid

approach consisting of spatial–spectral supervised classification and unsupervised segmentation for brain cancer detection during surgical operations. The classification and segmentation results, generated by support vector machines and a hierarchical k-means algorithm, respectively, are combined using majority voting to produce the final classification map. Ma et al. [11] use wavelet feature extraction and support vector machines for in vivo head and neck cancer detection from HSI images of mice. Maktabi et al. [10] compare support vector machines, random forest, multilayer perceptron (MLP), and k-nearest neighbors (KNN) to detect esophageal carcinoma in resected tissue. Among these algorithms, support vector machines achieve the best results.

Various recent BHSI classification works use convolutional neural networks (CNN). Huang et al. [12] address the problem of blood cell classification by combining a modulated Gabor wavelet kernel with convolutional kernels. Another blood cell classification approach proposed by Wang et al. [13] uses 3D convolutional attention networks. Halicek et al. [21] use three CNNs—2D-CNN, 3D-CNN, and Inception CNN—to classify the margins of head and neck cancer. The results of their classifier are superior to those of classical machine learning approaches like support vector machines, ensemble linear discriminant analysis, and random forest. This is due to CNNs' ability to exploit both spectral and spatial information. Weijtmans et al. [22] address the task of tumor detection using a dual stream network having both spectral and spatial branches, which outperforms methods relying only on spectral or spatial information.

There are only a limited number of works addressing a segmentation task on medical HSI [15]. Wang et al. [8] propose Hyper-net, a 3D convolutional network, to segment melanoma from hyperspectral pathology images. Trajanovski et al. [23] compare U-net based semantic segmentation methods and pixel-wise classification methods for tongue tumor detection. Other applications of segmentation in BHSI include semantic organ segmentation [14] and brain tumor segmentation [24].

The results of our literature review suggest a scarcity of publicly available biomedical hyperspectral datasets. This can be attributed to ethical and privacy reasons, as well as the difficulty of obtaining hyperspectral data and corresponding ground-truth labels in the biomedical field. Notably, in some cases, the amount of labeled data constitutes only a small percentage of the given hyperspectral image. Most of the works we have encountered rely on private datasets. The few publicly available datasets we have found include [25] and [26].

III. DEEP LEARNING METHODS FOR HSI CLASSIFICATION

The task of HSI classification has been extensively studied in the field of remote sensing. This section reviews various DL approaches from the remote sensing literature for HSI classification. From these, we selected 20 different models and adapted these techniques for medical HSI. Their details—such as the year of publication, code implementation link,

FIGURE 1. The taxonomy of models considered for medical HSI classification. The models are grouped by architecture type: CNNs (red), RNNs (orange), transformers (green), and GNNs (blue). Additionally, the intensity of the color indicates whether the model was originally designed for HSI (darker shade) or RGB (lighter shade) data. For instance, for CNNs, models initially developed for HSI are shown in dark red, while those designed for RGB data are shown in light red. The type of outline around each model indicates the context in which it was trained: solid outlines represent spatial and spectral contexts, densely dashed outlines—spectral context only, and sparsely dashed outlines—spatial context only.

type of architecture, and further technical specifications—are presented in Table 1.

These models were selected based on the following criteria.

- Diversity in architecture types: A wide range of models was chosen to reflect different types of DL architectures for HSI classification. This includes CNNs, recurrent neural networks (RNNs), transformers, and graph neural networks (GNNs). By incorporating diverse approaches, we aim to explore how different architectural paradigms handle HSI data.
- Diversity in the utilization of combinations of HSI axes for information propagation: The selected models tackle the task of HSI classification from different perspectives. Some models focus solely on spectral information, others on spatial information, while some incorporate both spatial and spectral data. This variety covers the multiple state-of-the-art strategies for processing HSI, maximizing the chances of capturing all relevant information.
- Code availability in PyTorch: We considered only models for which source code was publicly available in PyTorch. This ensures reproducibility and enables ease of adaptation for future work.

A collection of various HSI classification approaches was previously constructed in [27] and [28]. This collection was later extended in [29] and [30] with the important addition of various DL architectures. We extend our comparative pool of algorithms with 24 additional entries from these collections to extend the representation of different DL and classical ML architectures. These additional models, listed in Table 2, include 16 CNN/transformer models originally designed for image segmentation, 3 classical ML models, a multilayer perceptron, and 4 baseline CNN models. These methods provide a fundamental point of reference for comparing the performance of the more advanced deep learning approaches.

This section categorizes HSI classification models based on both their architectural types and the spatial/spectral contexts in which they process the data. We classify the models into four major architecture types: CNNs, RNNs, transformers, and GNNs. Additionally, we subgroup them based on the type of the context: spatial, spectral, or a combination of both.

The taxonomy in Fig. 1 provides a clear visualization of how the different architectures approach the classification of hyperspectral images and shows which contexts (spatial, spectral, or both) are leveraged by each model. Additionally, color intensity highlights whether the model was originally proposed for HSI or for color images.

TABLE 1. The summarized review of models for HSI medical image classification. Note that model Yang does not have an associated paper the code was retrieved from DeepHyperX.

References	Year	Implementation GitHub	Architecture	Details
Hu et al. [31]	2015	xiachangxue/DeepHyperX	CNN	Processes each spectral signature using CNN layers.
Chen et al. [32]	2016	xiachangxue/DeepHyperX	CNN	Extracts spectral–spatial features using 3D-CNN layers.
S-CNN [33]	2016	xiachangxue/DeepHyperX	CNN	Uses 3D CNN, Treating each band as a separate image
Lee et al. [34]	2016	xiachangxue/DeepHyperX	CNN	Applies 3D CNN, jointly exploiting spatial and spectral features.
He et al. [35]	2017	xiachangxue/DeepHyperX	CNN	Learns 2D multi-scale spatial feature and 1D spectral feature from HSI.
Li et al. [36]	2017	xiachangxue/DeepHyperX	CNN	Processes spectral–spatial-combined features using lightweight 3D-CNN.
Mou et al. [37]	2017	xiachangxue/DeepHyperX	RNN	Represent the pixels of hyperspectral images via a sequential perspective and processes them using RNN.
Hamida et al. [38]	2018	AminaBh	CNN	Proposes 3D CNN approach that enables a joint spectral and spatial information processing.
Luo et al. [39]	2018	xiachangxue/DeepHyperX	CNN	Replaces the output layer of CNN with XGBoost.
HybridSN [40]	2019	Pancakerr/HybridSN	CNN	Facilitates spectral-spatial 3D-CNN followed by spatial 2D-CNN.
CEGCN [41]	2020	qichaoliu/CNN_Enhanced_GC	CNN, GNN	Combines CNN and GCN branches performing feature learning on small-scale regular regions and large-scale irregular regions.
Sellars et al. [42]	2020	psellcam	GNN	Extracts spectral and spatial features from superpixel regions and uses them to produce a contracted weighted graph-representation.
ASSMN [43]	2020	DotWang/SSGRN	RNN	Utilizes ConvLSTM and LSTM layers for spectral and spatial feature extraction.
FullyContNet [44]	2021	DotWang/FullyContNet	CNN	Consists of a 3D CNN and a cascaded network that utilizes PAM and CAM to extract multiscale features.
SpectralFormer [45]	2021	danfenghong	Transformer	Learns group-wise spectral embeddings from local sequences in neighboring bands, additionally boosts model performance through an adaptive cross-layer fusion module.
Yang	2022	xiachangxue/DeepHyperX	CNN	Classifies HSI using a combination of both 2D and 3D convolutions to capture spectral and spatial features.
HIT [29]	2022	xiachangxue/DeepHyperX	CNN, Transformer	Transformer-based method that extracts local spatial and long-term spectral information using 3D CNN layers.
GiGCN [46]	2022	ShuGuoJ/GiGCN	GNN	Consists of internal and external graphs that hierarchically extract feature representations from the inside and outside of superpixels, respectively.
WFCG [47]	2022	quanweiliu/WFCG	CNN, GNN	Combines superpixel-based graph attention module with pixel-based CNN module.
SS-ConvNeXt [48]	2023	ZHUYMGeo/SS-ConvNeXt	CNN, Transformer	Adopts ConvNeXt, a hybrid architecture that incorporates elements of both convolutional networks and transformer models, for HSI by applying it to both spectral and spatial contexts.

A. CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS

In the field of hyperspectral image classification, CNNs have emerged as the predominant deep learning methodology. In CNN models, a set of kernels (filters) is utilized to extract and learn diverse spectral and/or spatial features.

Pixel-wise spectral processing CNNs (Figure 2 top branch) consider each pixel as a separate data point and treat the whole HSI cube as a collection of spectral vectors. These approaches ignore the spatial context and extract features based on the spectral context only. While spectral features alone provide enough information to differentiate materials and textures within HSI, these approaches suffer from the lack of spatial context [67], which may lead to misclassification in areas with similar spectral but different spatial features.

Typically, spectral processing architectures utilize 1D CNNs along the spectral dimension [68]. Alternatively, Hu et al. [31] propose to regard pixel vectors as 2D images with height equal to 1 and process them by applying a 2D CNN with kernels of size $k \times 1$, where k is the number of spectral bands.

Spatial processing approaches treat HSI as color images by applying 2D convolutions to the spatial dimensions.

These methods effectively capture spatial structure and relationships between pixels. The most common way of processing HSI using 2D CNNs is to treat spectral bands as image channels. However, the correlations among spectral bands within a pixel are ignored, which potentially leads to sub-optimal feature extraction. To mitigate this issue, S-CNN [33] processes each band of HSI as a separate image and then utilizes majority voting to obtain the final segmentation mask. This can lead to increased computational complexity and memory requirements for the model due to a large number of input images.

Recent advancements have attempted to address the limitations of spectral-only and spatial-only processing by integrating spectral information into the spatial processing framework. There are three primary methods of combining spectral and spatial information: 3D CNNs, multiscale CNNs, and hybrid approaches.

3D CNNs apply convolutions across both the spectral and spatial dimensions simultaneously, capturing joint spectral–spatial features.

Pixel-neighborhood-wise 3D CNNs (Figure 2 bottom branch) consider the spectral information not only

TABLE 2. The summarized review of baseline models for image classification.

References	Year	Implementation	GitHub	Architecture	Details
Models designed for general image segmentation [30]					
R-CNN [49]	2014	rbgirshick/rcnn		CNN	First proposes regions of interest within an image and then classifies those using a CNN.
ViT [50]	2020	xiachangxue/DeepHyperX		Transformer	Interprets an image as a sequence of patches and process it by a standard Transformer encod.
LocalViT [51]	2021	xiachangxue/DeepHyperX		CNN, Transformer	Incorporate a locality mechanism into vision transformers by adding 2D depth-wise convolutions.
T2T-ViT [52]	2021	xiachangxue/DeepHyperX		Transformer	Structurizes the image to tokens by recursively aggregating neighboring tokens into one token.
PiT [53]	2021	naver-ai/pit		CNN, Transformer	Incorporates a pooling layer into ViT.
DeepViT [54]	2021	zhoudaquan/dvit_repo		Transformer	Introduces re-attention mechanism to solve attention collapse problem of ViT.
CrossViT [55]	2021	IBM/CrossViT		Transformer	Introduced dual-branch vision transformer the branches of which exchange information using cross-attention mechanism.
LeViT [56]	2021	facebookresearch/LeViT		CNN, Transformer	Replaces linear projection layers with convolution embedding layers in ViT.
CvT [57]	2021	microsoft/CvT		CNN, Transformer	Introduces convolutional token embedding and convolutional projection to ViT.
CaiT [58]	2021	facebookresearch/deit		Transformer	Adds learnable diagonal matrix after residual block, and introduces class-attention layers in an encoder/decoder architecture to separate self-attention layers from class-attention layers.
TNT [59]	2021	huawei-noah/CV-Backbones		Transformer	Divides the local patches to further smaller patches and process them using outer and inner transformer block respectively.
ViP [60]	2021	houqb/VisionPermutator		Transformer	Separately encodes the feature representations along the height and width dimensions with linear projections.
ViP-P	2021	xiachangxue/DeepHyperX		Transformer	Modifies base implementation of ViP by applying self-attention across permuted dimensions: height, width, channels, instead of using only MLP.
iFormer [61]	2022	sail-sg/iFormer		Transformer	learns comprehensive features with both high- and low-frequency information by integrating the advantages of convolution, max-pooling, and self-attention.
Wave-Vit [62]	2022	YehLi/ImageNetModel		Transformer	Formulates the invertible down-sampling with wavelet transforms and self-attention learning in a unified way.
RVT [63]	2022	xiachangxue/DeepHyperX		Transformer	Leverages robust components of ViTs as building blocks.
Baseline models [28]					
SVM [64]		-		ML	Support vector machine model.
KNN		-		ML	K-nearest neighbors algorithm.
SGD		-		ML	
MLP		-		MLP	Multilayer perceptron.
Convolution 2D/3D [65]	1998	-		CNN	Several 2D or 3D CNN layers.
Involution 2D/3D [66]	2021	d-li14/involution		CNN	Inverts the design principles of convolution by using distinct spatial extent kernels shared across channels.

of the current pixel but also of its neighboring pixels. Chen et al. [32], Li et al. [36], and Luo et al. [39] extract image cubes from HSI to form the training dataset. These cubes are then processed and classified using 3D CNNs.

Full-context 3D CNN approaches, unlike patch-based methods (which classify a target pixel using local information in a fixed-size area around it), directly feed the whole HSI cube into the 3D CNN to classify all pixels at once. FullyContNet [44] consists of two main components: a backbone that uses multiple 3D convolutional layers to process the entire HSI and a cascaded network that utilizes position attention modules (PAM) and channel attention modules (CAM) to extract multilevel features. The main drawback of processing HSI using 3D CNNs is their high computational demand. Due to the high number of spectral

bands, substantial amounts of memory and processing power are required.

Multiscale CNNs employ convolutional layers with varying receptive field sizes instead of processing the entire image at once. This allows multiscale networks to effectively process both fine and coarse details within the HSI. Although this approach is prone to increased model complexity and training time, it proves particularly effective for complex scenes with diverse spatial resolutions. He et al. [35] propose a multiscale 3D CNN that applies 3D convolutional kernels of different sizes and combines their results through summation at each layer. Meanwhile, Lee and Kwon [34] propose using separate branches for 3D convolutional blocks with $3 \times 3 \times 3$ and $1 \times 1 \times 1$ kernel sizes, where the features extracted from both branches are concatenated and further processed through a series of 3D convolutional blocks.

FIGURE 2. Visualization of types of HSI processing using CNNs: pixel-wise spectral processing (top) and pixel-neighborhood-wise processing (bottom).

Hybrid approaches use separate CNN branches for processing the spectral and spatial contexts. The embeddings obtained from these two branches are then merged and processed by the fusion layer. HybridSN [40] is a hybrid architecture that combines both 3D and 2D convolutional blocks. In this model, a 3D block is initially used for joint spatial–spectral feature learning, followed by 2D blocks that focus solely on spatial features. This approach not only reduces the computational complexity of the network by minimizing the number of 3D convolutional layers but also enhances performance, compared to pure 3D CNN approaches, particularly for classes with similar textures. Hamida et al. [38] propose a method that employs a stack of 3D blocks followed by a set of 1D blocks to emphasize spectral information for each pixel.

FIGURE 3. Visualization of spectral processing using RNNs.

B. RECURRENT NEURAL NETWORKS

All the previously discussed CNN methods treat the pixels in HSI as vectors. However, due to the continuous nature of spectral information, there is a strong internal correlation among the spectral bands in HSI. Thus, some approaches consider the pixels as sequences rather than vectors. RNNs and their variants, such as gated recurrent units (GRUs) [69]

and long short-term memory (LSTM) [70] networks, have been widely utilized in the field of natural language processing to capture the temporal variability of long sentences. Given that pixels in HSIs can also be considered sequential data—reflecting spectral variability as reflectance/emission changes with wavelength—it is natural to utilize RNNs for HSI processing. Different approaches can be used to leverage RNNs in HSI classification, focusing on either per-pixel spectral processing or combined spectral–spatial processing.

Pixel-wise spectral processing models treat each pixel in HSI as a separate sequence of spectral values across different wavelengths (Fig. 3). These networks learn to capture the relationships between different spectral bands, distinguishing between different materials and textures in HSI data. Mou et al. [37] use an LSTM network with a time step equal to the number of spectral bands. Similar to pixel-wise spectral processing CNNs, the shortcoming of ignoring the spatial context persists.

Spectral–spatial processing methods integrate spatial information into RNNs by either combining them with CNNs or sequentializing the spatial context of a pixel.

Hybrid RNN–CNN methods apply spectral processing using RNNs to capture the spectral dependencies at each pixel and integrate spatial processing through the use of CNNs. These two units can either be applied sequentially [71], [72] or in parallel using separate branches for each type of information. Hang et al. [71] introduce the concept of cascaded RNNs, which create connections between multiple RNN layers to enhance model performance. In this model, the cascaded recurrent block is applied to features extracted by a 2D CNN. Xu et al. [73] utilize a dual-branch architecture, with an RNN dedicated to spectral feature extraction and a 2D CNN for spatial features.

Pure RNN models process both the spectral and the spatial information within the HSI. For example, Zhou et al. [74] split HSI patches from the first principal component along the row direction, feeding the sequence of these rows into an LSTM network. A significant limitation of this approach is the loss of the original spatial structure in the HSI when transforming the multidimensional data into a 1D sequence. To address this issue and to better capture spatial information while preserving the shape of the input data, Shi et al. [75] develop the concept of convolutional LSTM (ConvLSTM). ConvLSTM builds upon the foundation of LSTM, replacing the fully connected layers within the gates with convolutional layers. This allows the network to retain spatial structure while modeling spectral dependencies. The concept of ConvLSTM has been further explored in combination with both 2D and 3D CNNs [76], as well as in bidirectional ConvLSTM architectures [77]. Building on the concept of ConvLSTM, ASSMN [43] leverages multiscale features and adaptively learns parameters to combine spectral and spatial features more effectively. This adaptive strategy allows ASSMN to dynamically balance the contributions of spectral and spatial information, improving the overall HSI classification performance.

C. TRANSFORMERS

Transformers were originally proposed to effectively process sequential data in natural language processing. By utilizing self-attention mechanisms, transformers extract global features and learn long-distance dependency relations inside input data. Transformers can be utilized to extract features from hyperspectral images through data sequentialization. This can be done in several ways.

Pixel-wise spectral processing methods interpret the continuous spectral bands of a single HSI pixel as a sequential data stream, where the entire pixel spectrum forms a sequence. This approach allows the model to capture the spectral dependencies across the bands effectively.

Spatial processing transformers are utilized to extract spatial context, generating feature embeddings from one or more channels of the input patches. Spatial transformers can be applied in several ways, as follows.

Features extracted by convolution: Spatial transformers can be applied to features extracted by 2D convolutional blocks [78]. The convolutional blocks first capture localized spatial information from HSI patches, and transformers then model the global spatial relationships.

Cascaded approach: An alternative method involves stacking multiple transformer encoders in a cascaded manner [45], where each layer progressively refines

the spatial feature representations, capturing deeper and more complex spatial structures.

Flattened feature maps: Some methods apply transformers directly to flattened feature maps extracted by CNNs [79], [80]. In this approach, the spatial context is preserved and modeled by the transformer layers, which process the feature maps as sequences to capture spatial dependencies across the image.

Spectral-spatial processing transformers merge spectral and spatial processing pathways, enabling the extraction of rich, context-aware features from both domains.

Spectrum word vector methods consider each pixel's spectrum as a word vector. He et al. [81] apply BERT [82] directly on the flattened patches where each pixel is considered a word vector.

Parallel processing methods use two separate transformer branches: one focusing on spectral HSI features and the other on spatial features [83]. The spectral transformer processes the spectrum of each pixel as a sequence, capturing dependencies across wavelengths. Simultaneously, the spatial transformer focuses on the spatial relationships between neighboring pixels within the image. The outputs from these two branches are then fused, either through concatenation or attention mechanisms, to produce a combined feature representation that reflects both spectral and spatial information. Alternatively, HIT [29] encodes spatial-spectral features of the HSI using three different branches along vertical, horizontal and spectral dimensions.

Sequential processing methods rely on a sequence of two transformers for the spectral and spatial information, respectively [48], [84]. The model first applies a transformer to capture spectral dependencies across the bands for each pixel. The resulting spectral features are then processed by another transformer (or reusing the same transformer block) to capture spatial relationships, successfully linking spectral and spatial contexts within the same feature space.

D. GRAPH NEURAL NETWORKS

The so-far discussed deep learning models are primarily designed to handle Euclidean data, thus, they often fail to account for the inherent correlations between adjacent regions in HSI. This is due to the fact that these models typically process data in regular grid structures, such as images or sequences, and therefore do not effectively capture the complex spatial relationships present in HSIs.

Recently, graph convolutional networks (GCNs) have gained significant attention due to their capability to perform convolution operations on data represented as graphs, which can have arbitrary structures. This feature allows GCNs to go beyond the constraints of traditional deep learning models by encoding HSI data into a graph format. In this graph representation, each pixel or superpixel is treated as a node, and the edges between nodes represent the correlations or

FIGURE 4. Superpixel-based graph construction. Each superpixel corresponds to a node in the graph. An edge is formed between two nodes if the corresponding superpixels have adjacent pixels.

similarities between adjacent regions. Explicitly encoding these correlations enables the model to capture and utilize the complex spatial dependencies that exist in the HSI data.

There are three main ways of graph construction based on HSI data, as presented below.

Pixel-based methods treat each pixel in the HSI cube as a node in the graph, and edges are established based on spatial proximity or spectral similarity. Pixel-based graph construction can be done in various ways, as detailed below.

KNN: Qin et al. [85] propose a GCN architecture that constructs a graph via KNN. Nodes are connected to their k -nearest neighbors in a local window based on Euclidean distance or spectral similarity, capturing the spatial or spectral context.

Fully connected graphs: The graph can be constructed in such a way that every pixel is connected to every other pixel. This approach enables the model to capture global dependencies; however, it has a higher computational cost. To combat this issue, Yang et al. [86] limit the graph size by focusing on the local topology of nodes rather than the entire graph. Alternatively, Hong et al. [87] construct a graph in the latent feature space using only labeled pixels, with the central pixel features in square regions pre-extracted by a CNN.

Superpixel-based methods utilize clusters of pixels that share similar characteristics and are grouped together to reduce the complexity of image processing tasks. The label assigned to a superpixel is determined by the most common category label within that superpixel. When the size of the training dataset is small, the division of the image into superpixels allows some unknown labels to be inferred from the superpixel's majority label, effectively increasing the number of labeled samples and thereby improving classification accuracy. Thus, the usage of superpixel methods can boost the performance of the model for HSI images, particularly when only a limited number of labeled pixels are available. A graph is constructed from superpixels by treating each one as a node and connecting nodes with edges based on spatial adjacency (Fig. 4). Wan et al. [88] and Sellars et al. [42] construct superpixels based on spectral similarity and spatial adjacency of pixels. The graphs are constructed by introducing edges between superpixels of different number of neighbor hops.

Hierarchical graph structures involve constructing graphs at multiple levels of granularity, such as pixel-level, superpixel-level, and region-level [46]. Using GNNs, the information is then propagated across different levels. This method of graph construction enables the GNN model to integrate fine-grained details with broader contextual information.

Instead of using only GNNs, some approaches [41], [47] combine them with CNNs to capture both spectral-spatial features and long-range relations between regions. The CNN branch extracts feature maps that represent the spectral and spatial characteristics of the data, while the GNN branch focuses on the topological relationships between pixels/superpixels.

IV. DATASET

The pre-clinical HSI dataset used in this comparative study comprises RF-ablated left atrial (LA) tissue from four porcine and five bovine hearts. These data were acquired as part of previous studies at the Sarvazyan lab at the George Washington University [5], [7], [89], [90]. The choice of LA endocardial surface as a target tissue to ablate was determined by the fact that the majority of atrial fibrillation sources are found at this anatomical location and that is where RF lesions are placed clinically. The application of RF energy eliminates abnormal sources of electrical activity while also changing the cardiac muscle autofluorescence profile. In humans, however, these changes can be obscured by the presence of a highly reflective and fluorescent layer of collagen, the major component of the LA endocardial surface. The average thickness of such a layer in humans is greater than that of porcine tissue but less than that of bovine tissue [91]. The thinner layer of endocardial collagen in porcine LA allows for more consistent unmixing results, whereas the thicker layer of the collagenous endocardium in bovine LA makes revealing RF lesions more challenging. Animal hearts were sourced from either local abattoirs or obtained after surgical training at the George Washington Institute of Surgical Education and Research. Immediately after excision, tissues were transported to the lab facility on ice and dissected to expose the LA surface for ablation. RF energy was administered using a non-irrigated ablation catheter perpendicularly to the endocardial surface. Ablation durations ranged from 5 to 30 seconds, with tip temperatures between 50 and 70°C, close to clinical RF ablation therapy settings. The tissue was illuminated using a 365 nm UV light source (Precision LED Spotlight from Mightex, Pleasanton, CA) positioned at a 5 cm distance from the tissue surface. Hyperspectral cubes were acquired from 420–720 nm using Nuance FX system (PerkinElmer/Cri, Waltham, MA, USA) fitted with Nikon AF Micro-Nikkor 60 mm f/2.8D lens. The Nuance FX system comprises a liquid crystal tunable filter (CRi LCTF) and a monochromatic charged coupled device (Sony ICX285 CCD) [7]. Subsequent post-processing of HSI datasets using the commercial Nuance software

enabled differentiation of unablated and ablated tissues through supervised linear unmixing (LU), analyzing spectral differences between defined regions of interest (ROI).

The standard procedure to confirm the presence of ablated tissue is to immerse samples into a 1% 2,3,5-triphenyltetrazolium chloride (TTC) solution, which stains the viable muscle red while leaving ablated tissue unstained. Yet, such manipulations, as well as attempts to peel the endocardial collagen layer, distort the tissue, making it impossible to reveal the truth on a pixel by pixel level. Therefore, for the datasets used in this study, as well as for biological tissues in general, one of the main challenges is the lack of reliable ground truth labels for training DL models. Grading tissues often depends on subjective expert interpretations, leading to inconsistencies and biases. Without accurate labels, models risk overfitting to noisy or incomplete data. Variability in tissue samples (e.g., between animals or among different biological conditions) further complicates generalization. In an effort to mitigate this shortcoming, we involve researchers who regularly use HSI for their studies and students who took a bioimaging course in HSI, and then use their combined inputs as a voting system to validate algorithm outputs.

In the following experimental comparison of the HSI classification algorithms, we include an additional contender: the LU functionality of the Nuance 3 software that is a part of the Nuance FX system. In order to convert the linear unmixing results into binary classification masks, a pixel is classified with its maximum value among the different selected components.

V. QUANTITATIVE EVALUATION

A. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In our quantitative experiment, we assess the performance of the 45 existing HSI classification algorithms. For the training and testing pipeline, a bioimaging expert in our team generated several sets of ROIs for each HSI datacube. Specifically, per datacube, nine sets of ROIs were created: ‘AA’, ‘AB’, ‘AC’, ‘BA’, ‘BB’, ‘BC’, ‘CA’, ‘CB’, and ‘CC’. Each set of ROIs contains two rectangular ROIs: one representing the ablated area and the other representing the unablated area. The set names reflect the reliability of ROI selection: the first letter refers to the ablated area ROI and the second letter—to the unablated area ROI. According to expert assessment, ‘A’ indicates the highest reliability, while ‘C’ is the lowest. Examples for each ROI type are shown in Fig. 5.

Per datacube, we performed nine train–test experiments. In each experiment, a single set of ROIs was used for training. The other eight sets of ROIs were used for testing, excluding any regions intersecting with the training ROIs. After obtaining the test results, we calculated the average performance across all nine runs. To aggregate algorithm performance across datacubes, we averaged the scores across the multiple porcine and bovine datacubes, respectively.

FIGURE 5. An example from the porcine dataset, highlighting regions ‘A’, ‘B’, and ‘C’ for each class. Red rectangles denote the ablated regions, while green rectangles represent the unablated regions. HSI is visualized by adding the individual spectral bands.

B. EVALUATION METRICS

We use a set of three statistical evaluation metrics. The primary metric employed is overall accuracy (OA), which measures the proportion of correctly classified instances out of the total predictions. Additionally, we apply average accuracy (AA), which calculates the mean accuracy for each class, providing a balanced evaluation across classes. To further analyze the agreement between predicted and actual classifications, we use the Kappa statistic, or Cohen’s Kappa (κ), a measure of inter-rater agreement for categorical data. This metric ranges from -1 (complete disagreement) to 1 (perfect agreement), with 0 indicating agreement at the level of chance. It is given by the formula:

$$\kappa = \frac{p_o - p_e}{1 - p_e}, \quad (1)$$

where p_o is the observed agreement, and p_e is the expected agreement between the ground truth mask and the classifier output.

For all metrics, we report mean and standard deviation. OA and AA are reported as percentages. The Kappa statistic (κ) is multiplied by 100.

C. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3 presents the performance of all algorithms on the porcine dataset, sorted by OA. Table 4 shows the results for the bovine dataset in a similar format. For each table, a line separates the ten best-performing algorithms and the rest. The average scores of all algorithms per datacube are additionally provided in Appendix B.

For both porcine and bovine datasets, the top three performers are consistently the same. These are GiGCN [46], CEGCN [41], and Nuance LU, with OAs of 96.79%, 91.95%, and 89.85% on the porcine dataset, and 94.41%, 93.93%, and 85.80% on the bovine dataset, respectively. Both GiGCN and CEGCN employ GNNs, whereas the algorithm behind Nuance LU is outlined in [92] and [93].

TABLE 3. Performance of all algorithms on the porcine dataset, ranked by OA scores. Per algorithm, average OA, AA, and κ scores are reported, along with respective standard deviations. A horizontal line separates the top ten algorithms from the rest. Row coloring is in accordance with the taxonomy in Fig. 1.

Model Name	OA (%)	AA (%)	κ ($\times 100$)
GiGCN	96.79 \pm 12.66	97.08 \pm 11.45	94.18 \pm 22.90
CEGCN	91.95 \pm 18.62	92.33 \pm 17.29	84.81 \pm 34.52
Nuance LU	89.85 \pm 13.71	90.04 \pm 12.94	79.81 \pm 26.65
MLP	86.24 \pm 14.41	86.13 \pm 14.79	71.66 \pm 29.96
SS-ConvNeXt	84.08 \pm 14.04	84.29 \pm 14.15	67.90 \pm 27.83
CvT	82.68 \pm 17.27	82.76 \pm 17.88	64.46 \pm 35.27
LeViT	80.93 \pm 18.03	81.00 \pm 17.24	61.77 \pm 34.57
Hamida et al.	79.18 \pm 14.88	78.61 \pm 15.39	56.93 \pm 30.38
Sellars et al.	78.53 \pm 15.09	76.90 \pm 16.04	54.44 \pm 31.82
iFormer	78.45 \pm 16.36	78.94 \pm 16.05	56.84 \pm 31.51
He et al.	77.75 \pm 18.10	77.72 \pm 18.11	54.78 \pm 35.67
HIT	76.98 \pm 15.51	76.71 \pm 15.85	52.91 \pm 30.97
SGD	76.57 \pm 17.41	75.82 \pm 18.22	51.19 \pm 35.73
ASSMN	75.68 \pm 14.89	75.20 \pm 15.46	49.96 \pm 30.34
Convolution 2D	75.64 \pm 17.62	75.48 \pm 18.49	50.20 \pm 35.55
R-CNN	75.14 \pm 14.37	74.30 \pm 15.50	48.09 \pm 29.82
WFCG	74.04 \pm 20.41	67.85 \pm 30.42	46.89 \pm 40.15
FullyContNet	74.03 \pm 21.81	73.52 \pm 22.73	46.58 \pm 43.48
RVT	73.28 \pm 18.52	73.70 \pm 17.40	47.11 \pm 34.43
Lee et al.	72.61 \pm 20.51	73.50 \pm 19.72	46.34 \pm 38.05
SVM	72.60 \pm 19.28	71.85 \pm 19.81	43.60 \pm 37.62
ViP-P	72.39 \pm 19.50	72.31 \pm 20.49	43.76 \pm 38.19
Li et al.	72.24 \pm 18.90	72.09 \pm 18.68	44.04 \pm 35.66
Convolution 3D	70.54 \pm 17.95	69.83 \pm 18.83	39.30 \pm 35.47
Wave-ViT	70.53 \pm 18.93	70.21 \pm 19.91	39.73 \pm 37.02
KNN	70.45 \pm 18.03	69.72 \pm 18.60	39.30 \pm 34.78
Mou et al.	70.42 \pm 19.17	69.74 \pm 19.88	40.03 \pm 36.40
HybridSN	69.46 \pm 17.04	69.78 \pm 16.45	39.05 \pm 32.67
CaiT	69.18 \pm 17.60	68.94 \pm 18.50	37.12 \pm 34.21
DeepViT	69.14 \pm 18.81	69.38 \pm 19.56	37.89 \pm 36.05
SpectralFormer	69.03 \pm 18.54	68.73 \pm 18.86	37.13 \pm 35.19
Yang	68.82 \pm 18.37	68.61 \pm 19.34	36.43 \pm 35.66
T2T-ViT	68.68 \pm 16.77	69.10 \pm 16.50	39.07 \pm 32.81
Involution 3D	68.08 \pm 18.90	67.12 \pm 18.73	36.28 \pm 34.20
CrossViT	67.94 \pm 17.76	67.63 \pm 18.35	34.78 \pm 34.00
Luo et al.	66.92 \pm 18.75	66.59 \pm 18.82	33.09 \pm 35.40
ViP	66.73 \pm 18.93	66.95 \pm 18.35	34.76 \pm 32.09
Involution 2D	66.16 \pm 17.18	66.00 \pm 17.99	35.17 \pm 31.49
LocalViT	65.50 \pm 18.60	65.30 \pm 18.65	30.37 \pm 35.58
TNT	65.23 \pm 19.18	64.89 \pm 19.03	29.75 \pm 35.81
ViT	64.58 \pm 19.86	64.76 \pm 19.93	29.08 \pm 37.14
S-CNN	63.83 \pm 27.44	63.91 \pm 27.31	35.91 \pm 39.49
PiT	62.43 \pm 17.30	62.90 \pm 17.23	24.74 \pm 32.55
Hu et al.	50.75 \pm 8.94	50.00 \pm 0.00	0.00 \pm 0.00
Chen et al.	50.75 \pm 8.94	50.00 \pm 0.00	0.00 \pm 0.00

The bovine dataset, generally, poses a more difficult classification task due to anatomical features like a thicker collagen layer. As a consequence, lower average scores and higher standard deviations are consistently observed for the bovine dataset, compared to the porcine dataset. This confirms the greater complexity of the task and indicates model instability for this data. Despite the differences of the two datasets, the algorithms in the top-ten positions for both cases have a large overlap. In particular, eight algorithms (GiGCN, CEGCN, Nuance LU, MLP, SS-ConvNeXt, LeViT, Sellars et al., iFormer) appear in the top-ten positions for both datasets. The other two top-ten algorithms for porcine data are CvT and Hamida et al. For bovine data, the two algorithms are HybridSN and WFCG.

TABLE 4. Performance of all algorithms on the bovine dataset, ranked by OA scores. Per algorithm, average OA, AA, and κ scores are reported, along with respective standard deviations. A horizontal line separates the top ten algorithms from the rest. Row coloring is in accordance with the taxonomy in Fig. 1.

Model Name	OA (%)	AA (%)	κ ($\times 100$)
GiGCN	94.41 \pm 14.07	93.05 \pm 16.53	86.09 \pm 33.08
CEGCN	93.93 \pm 16.03	93.32 \pm 16.26	86.80 \pm 32.27
Nuance LU	85.80 \pm 11.47	85.90 \pm 11.93	67.76 \pm 24.33
HybridSN	78.88 \pm 18.33	79.20 \pm 18.17	54.80 \pm 35.57
Sellars et al.	78.25 \pm 18.53	76.61 \pm 18.87	50.25 \pm 36.82
SS-ConvNeXt	76.56 \pm 16.80	77.77 \pm 16.28	51.99 \pm 33.20
MLP	74.26 \pm 20.64	74.00 \pm 20.75	45.45 \pm 40.87
LeViT	67.58 \pm 24.33	69.62 \pm 22.77	38.21 \pm 42.67
WFCG	66.14 \pm 27.27	73.12 \pm 25.65	39.13 \pm 41.34
iFormer	65.27 \pm 22.34	68.01 \pm 21.60	33.79 \pm 41.48
CvT	64.79 \pm 22.21	68.03 \pm 22.18	33.15 \pm 40.66
He et al.	64.15 \pm 22.36	66.34 \pm 21.06	30.54 \pm 40.04
FullyContNet	64.11 \pm 22.36	66.10 \pm 21.21	30.09 \pm 40.58
Convolution 2D	63.80 \pm 22.21	65.55 \pm 21.12	30.44 \pm 39.60
Lee et al.	63.38 \pm 20.95	65.43 \pm 20.46	28.49 \pm 38.57
SVM	63.28 \pm 22.36	65.15 \pm 21.25	28.48 \pm 40.09
RVT	63.06 \pm 21.84	65.59 \pm 19.88	28.62 \pm 38.49
HIT	62.82 \pm 21.98	64.22 \pm 20.75	26.67 \pm 39.84
ASSMN	62.44 \pm 20.91	65.33 \pm 19.60	27.89 \pm 36.84
Hamida et al.	62.40 \pm 20.93	64.43 \pm 19.56	26.57 \pm 37.57
SpectralFormer	62.07 \pm 21.53	64.50 \pm 20.33	26.87 \pm 38.21
SGD	61.95 \pm 22.50	65.02 \pm 21.37	28.49 \pm 39.76
Convolution 3D	61.45 \pm 21.04	64.14 \pm 20.19	25.96 \pm 38.34
Chen et al.	61.45 \pm 18.69	49.94 \pm 0.15	-0.09 \pm 0.24
Mou et al.	61.44 \pm 21.91	64.63 \pm 20.91	27.60 \pm 38.85
Hu et al.	61.43 \pm 18.88	50.02 \pm 0.19	0.04 \pm 0.35
KNN	61.39 \pm 21.63	63.55 \pm 20.43	25.40 \pm 38.65
ViP-P	61.34 \pm 22.56	63.83 \pm 21.88	26.47 \pm 40.69
ViP	60.98 \pm 20.36	62.69 \pm 19.96	22.98 \pm 36.79
TNT	60.90 \pm 19.95	62.46 \pm 18.81	22.45 \pm 35.38
ViT	60.67 \pm 21.54	61.93 \pm 19.94	23.22 \pm 37.65
T2T-ViT	60.67 \pm 20.09	62.48 \pm 18.52	22.86 \pm 34.44
CrossViT	60.67 \pm 19.78	62.42 \pm 18.97	22.37 \pm 36.15
DeepViT	60.59 \pm 19.91	62.45 \pm 19.66	22.49 \pm 36.84
LocalViT	60.57 \pm 21.51	62.81 \pm 20.54	23.37 \pm 38.98
Li et al.	60.44 \pm 21.09	62.11 \pm 20.06	22.37 \pm 38.00
Wave-ViT	60.40 \pm 21.46	62.71 \pm 21.21	24.11 \pm 39.48
Luo et al.	60.28 \pm 19.87	61.46 \pm 18.17	21.24 \pm 35.21
Involution 3D	60.18 \pm 21.75	61.06 \pm 20.64	24.12 \pm 37.48
CaiT	60.01 \pm 20.71	61.86 \pm 20.14	22.37 \pm 37.13
Yang	59.85 \pm 20.78	62.92 \pm 20.21	23.94 \pm 37.61
R-CNN	59.77 \pm 22.65	62.74 \pm 21.64	24.40 \pm 39.54
Involution 2D	58.44 \pm 22.20	60.55 \pm 20.00	23.49 \pm 35.60
PiT	56.48 \pm 18.41	58.95 \pm 17.07	15.78 \pm 31.30
S-CNN	47.80 \pm 30.51	51.75 \pm 29.78	19.24 \pm 36.72

Most of the best-performing algorithms incorporate spatial context only or combine spatial and spectral contexts. This confirms that the spatial neighborhood of a pixel is important for its correct classification. This also aligns with the chronological trends toward spatial/combined contexts observed in the reviewed algorithms. The few algorithms in our taxonomy with a spectral context are relatively old (e.g., Hu et al. [31] from 2015), while the newer algorithms typically converge towards additional utilization of spatial information. Among the eight algorithms in both top-ten lists, four were designed for HSI data (GiGCN, CEGCN, SS-ConvNeXt, Sellars et al.) and two for RGB (LeViT, iFormer); the other two are Nuance LU and MLP—a classical approach not specific to image type. However, outside the top-ten, HSI-specific models tend to outperform RGB-design models.

Models incorporating GNNs, e.g. GiGCN, CEGCN, and Sellars et al., consistently rank at the top. This is accredited to the utilization of superpixels for graph construction, which implicitly incorporates long-distance connections between pixels to enhance prediction accuracy. Thus, GNNs can achieve robust performance on small datasets. The Sellars et al. approach maintains comparable performance on both datasets, ranking ninth on porcine and fourth on bovine data, with an OA of about 78–79%. Interestingly, WFCG, the last GNN-based model, ranks only seventeenth on the porcine dataset, but jumps to the ninth position on the more complex bovine dataset. Numerically, WFCG achieves 74.04% OA on the porcine dataset and only 66.14% OA on the bovine dataset. The rank improvements are explained by the degraded performance of other algorithms on the bovine dataset.

Transformers are the second largest class of architectures among the top-ten high-performing models. However, they demonstrate lower effectiveness on these datasets compared to GNNs, likely due to transformers' tendency to require larger datasets for high accuracy. When moving from the porcine to the bovine dataset, one transformer model, CvT, drops out of the top ten, and two others, SS-ConvNeXt and LeViT, lose one position each, with OA reductions of around 8% and 13%, respectively. iFormer maintains its tenth position, although its OA declines by 13% on the bovine data. These findings suggest that, while transformers can architecturally handle the complex structure of bovine samples, they require training data much larger than two rectangular areas to fulfill their potential.

One CNN model appears among the top-ten performers for each dataset: Hamida et al. for porcine data and HybridSN for bovine data. This indicates that while CNNs are a crucial component in hybrid architectures for HSI classification and such components are commonly found in top-performing models, pure CNN models lack the capacity to effectively address the full complexity of this classification problem.

Our literature study revealed only a few RNN models for HSI classification. As a consequence, RNNs are under-represented in our comparative experiments. At the same time, the performance of the two models—ASSMN and Mou et al.—are not competitive. Our experiment demonstrates that these RNN models are not well-suited for the task at hand.

MLP is the only baseline model that ranks among the top ten for both porcine and bovine datasets. MLP, with its straightforward architecture and reliance solely on spectral information, performs particularly well on the porcine dataset. MLP has been shown to perform subpar to SVM in a previous biomedical HSI analysis task [10]. In our experiments on porcine and bovine heart tissue, MLP outperforms SVM, with 86.24% vs 72.60% OA for porcine and 74.26% vs 63.28% OA for bovine data, respectively. On the bovine data, MLP performance declines relative to more complex models, underscoring its limitations when handling more intricate tissue structures.

VI. QUALITATIVE EVALUATION

A. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Through an additional qualitative experiment, we compare the eight HSI classification algorithms that were among the top-ten performers in both porcine and bovine quantitative experiments. The algorithms include GNNs (GiGCN, CEGCN, Sellars et al.), transformers (SS-ConvNeXt, LeViT, iFormer), a baseline MLP model, and Nuance LU.

Due to the unavailability of reliable reference classification masks for the task at hand, our quantitative evaluation experiment provides only limited insights into the performance of different algorithms. In order to reveal complementary observations, we compare the algorithm performance based on the perception of observers with domain-specific knowledge. For fair comparison, we utilize the results obtained by training all algorithms on the 'AA'-labeled sets of ROIs. It should be noted that individual algorithms may perform better or worse on average with other training samples. Thus, judgments made based on 'AA'-labeled sets of ROIs only do not fully reflect the performance of a particular algorithm.

FIGURE 6. Visual comparison of eight top-performing models on a porcine atrial tissue sample. The red areas represent ablated tissue, while the green indicates unablated tissue.

Binary segmentation masks represent ablated and unablated tissues with two values only. This approach does not adequately convey the extent of RF ablation damage, making it less interpretable for human observation. To address this, RGB visualizations are generated for all competing algorithms. These RGB representations use smooth gradient transitions between colors to emphasize the distinction between ablated and unablated tissue regions. The visualization approach is detailed in Appendix C. For Nuance LU, its default RGB output serves as the visualization. Figure 6 illustrates the visualizations of the eight algorithms applied to one of the porcine datacubes. Visualizations for all other datacubes are provided in Appendix C.

A total of 17 participants are invited to the evaluation, including 9 specialists from the L. A. Orbeli Institute of Physiology NAS RA and 8 students who have completed the Biomedical Imaging and Cell Staining course at the American University of Armenia.

To facilitate a thorough evaluation, we develop an interactive application, using the `Psychopy` open source software package written in Python, that allows participants to rate the performance of the competing algorithms on all HSI cubes in our datasets. Each participant completes two sessions:

FIGURE 7. A screenshot of the qualitative evaluation process. It displays randomly shuffled outputs from the eight competing algorithms: seven ML methods and Nuance LU. Instructions on the screen, that specify the expected number of ablated regions, guide participants in rating the performance of each algorithm on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 represents ‘Poor,’ 2–‘Fair,’ 3–‘Average,’ 4–‘Good,’ and 5–‘Excellent.’ A sidebar is used to rate an algorithm, thus fractional scores can also be registered.

one for porcine data and another for bovine data. In each session, all HSI cubes are presented sequentially in a shuffled order. For every HSI cube, the user interface shows all eight visualizations and eight scalebars to assess each algorithm’s performance independently and in parallel. The scalebar goes from 1 to 5, where 1 indicates ‘Poor’, 2 indicates ‘Fair’, 3 indicates ‘Average’, 4 indicates ‘Good’, and 5 indicates ‘Excellent.’ Fractional scores can also be selected on the scalebar. For guidance, a textual cue describes how many regions have been ablated for that specific HSI sample. The user interface, depicted in Fig. 7 is designed for a screen resolution of 2560×1440 . A darkened engagement setting (Appendix D) using curtains is created to minimize distractions and encourage thoughtful evaluation.

FIGURE 8. The average score per classification algorithm in the subjective evaluation experiment, separately for porcine and bovine datasets. The algorithms are ordered in a non-increasing order of performance on the bovine dataset.

B. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 8 presents the experimental results in non-increasing order of average algorithm scores for the bovine dataset, with

FIGURE 9. Cartoon of experimental setup. TF—tunable filter. Images acquired at different wavelengths create a hyperspectral data cube. Spectral information from each pixel is then used to classify the pixels into different subtypes.

each model’s scores displayed for both porcine and bovine voting outcomes.

Nuance LU achieves the highest average scores on the porcine (3.61) and bovine (3.73) datasets, likely benefiting from specialists’ familiarity with the software. In contrast, DL model visualizations frequently display a yellow-shade circular area around the ablated region, signaling model uncertainty about the boundary placement. While this has potentially reduced specialists’ confidence in these models due to dissimilarity with the results of Nuance LU, the information about model uncertainty in certain regions can be highly valuable in clinical applications. Future work may consider explicitly quantifying the classification uncertainty to enhance the reliability of the models.

MLP, despite its simple design, earns a respectable score of 3.23, securing second place for the porcine dataset due to its reliable performance. However, its score drops to 2.30 for the bovine dataset. This is in agreement with its performance in the quantitative experiment, with MLP’s performance declining as data complexity increases.

GiGCN demonstrates strong performance in quantitative evaluations but receives comparatively lower qualitative scores due to its use of superpixels, which results in segmented visual representations. Its RGB visualization does not showcase smooth color gradient transitions. Rather, it shows ‘pixelated’ patterns around the superpixels. In contrast, Sellars et al. and CEGCN produce smoother visualizations, earning higher qualitative ratings. Both integrate GNNs with smaller superpixels; CEGCN also has a CNN component. Notably, these graph-based models excel in handling the more complex bovine dataset, with Sellars et al. and CEGCN currently securing second and third places, respectively, due to their architectures’ adaptability to intricate structures in the data.

Among transformers, LeViT performs the best, consistently ranking in fourth place for both datasets, with its score decreasing by only 0.32 from porcine to bovine. SS-ConvNeXt is the third for the porcine dataset but performs poorly on the bovine dataset, dropping to the sixth place with a score decrease of 0.78. iFormer ranks eighth, the lowest

FIGURE 10. Visual comparison of eight top-performing models on the porcine/bovine atrial tissue samples. The red areas represent ablated tissue, while the green indicates unablated tissue. The results for the porcine2 sample are in Fig. 6.

TABLE 5. Performance of all algorithms per datacube on the porcine dataset, ranked by overall OA scores. Per algorithm and per datacube, the OA average across the nine runs is reported, along with the standard deviation. A horizontal line separates the top ten algorithms from the rest. Row coloring is in accordance with the taxonomy in Fig. 1.

Model Name	porcine1 OA (%)	porcine2 OA (%)	porcine3 OA (%)	porcine4 OA (%)
GiGCN	79.87 ± 27.02	84.79 ± 7.46	74.50 ± 9.96	86.92 ± 9.24
CEGCN	80.18 ± 27.23	98.49 ± 1.62	84.11 ± 10.14	90.20 ± 8.35
Nuance LU	89.93 ± 8.17	98.32 ± 5.58	100.00 ± 0.00	89.23 ± 21.97
MLP	79.68 ± 14.47	100.00 ± 0.00	100.00 ± 0.00	94.87 ± 17.02
SS-ConvNeXt	71.79 ± 19.16	86.99 ± 11.29	80.01 ± 25.77	90.03 ± 12.01
CvT	54.04 ± 28.31	59.60 ± 8.47	53.19 ± 13.68	80.80 ± 25.75
LeViT	55.97 ± 21.56	66.28 ± 15.81	77.00 ± 12.29	72.12 ± 17.79
Hamida et al.	52.69 ± 26.68	60.30 ± 6.90	65.63 ± 9.62	80.91 ± 25.44
Sellars et al.	67.64 ± 17.30	74.55 ± 16.88	84.51 ± 11.85	82.47 ± 25.38
iFormer	59.36 ± 20.74	91.10 ± 8.79	89.10 ± 9.85	85.13 ± 14.90
He et al.	55.69 ± 29.37	82.24 ± 16.04	82.72 ± 14.44	85.15 ± 9.70
HIT	54.83 ± 25.28	90.75 ± 9.63	52.95 ± 15.27	85.66 ± 12.47
SGD	52.84 ± 29.81	57.78 ± 6.05	54.46 ± 13.88	81.73 ± 23.06
ASSMN	55.91 ± 22.12	99.24 ± 0.62	78.96 ± 11.36	89.40 ± 4.43
Liu et al.	53.56 ± 28.18	66.66 ± 15.92	85.19 ± 16.79	77.46 ± 23.80
R-CNN	53.98 ± 20.72	81.12 ± 11.50	82.72 ± 14.74	82.39 ± 20.59
WFCG	52.20 ± 6.38	61.47 ± 17.76	59.71 ± 16.17	76.56 ± 25.17
FullyContNet	49.78 ± 28.57	89.00 ± 8.76	72.81 ± 7.42	87.75 ± 3.83
RVT	52.06 ± 25.30	62.36 ± 8.63	81.35 ± 13.03	81.07 ± 25.72
Lee et al.	53.98 ± 26.15	63.52 ± 15.96	56.85 ± 18.66	83.44 ± 13.30
SVM	51.99 ± 25.91	91.51 ± 9.50	85.29 ± 17.12	80.03 ± 17.34
ViP-P	52.64 ± 31.28	79.21 ± 17.42	84.03 ± 17.23	84.87 ± 6.25
Li et al.	52.47 ± 26.83	98.87 ± 2.16	85.56 ± 16.87	80.36 ± 17.65
conv3d	52.74 ± 25.88	92.05 ± 8.85	85.49 ± 16.94	89.24 ± 5.55
Wave-ViT	52.34 ± 25.48	65.30 ± 11.74	79.03 ± 12.44	81.34 ± 26.49
KNN	52.09 ± 24.85	85.50 ± 10.94	78.73 ± 13.01	84.78 ± 12.51
Mou et al.	52.65 ± 27.10	54.40 ± 11.16	80.66 ± 12.59	79.62 ± 26.98
HybridSN	62.08 ± 7.71	88.31 ± 15.95	61.07 ± 17.77	77.71 ± 22.66
CaiT	56.21 ± 22.40	61.42 ± 8.04	77.30 ± 9.99	79.48 ± 25.93
DeepViT	58.20 ± 17.19	52.44 ± 5.16	46.62 ± 9.02	85.85 ± 8.08
SpectralFormer	51.63 ± 27.10	53.65 ± 14.50	55.66 ± 13.35	80.53 ± 24.85
Yang	51.23 ± 27.02	81.86 ± 13.30	79.87 ± 15.96	86.03 ± 5.73
T2T-ViT	60.82 ± 15.82	74.72 ± 9.71	80.17 ± 11.96	79.45 ± 24.20
Inception 3D	51.95 ± 16.96	46.04 ± 3.76	45.21 ± 6.37	59.54 ± 13.10
CrossViT	53.10 ± 24.65	60.18 ± 7.44	77.41 ± 8.48	79.65 ± 25.05
Luo et al.	49.75 ± 25.66	87.17 ± 14.66	57.49 ± 16.09	77.74 ± 24.22
ViP	57.22 ± 16.13	65.24 ± 14.61	50.54 ± 12.85	81.65 ± 24.25
Inception 2D	48.98 ± 24.24	46.04 ± 3.76	45.21 ± 6.37	59.54 ± 13.10
LocalViT	55.29 ± 24.42	63.89 ± 10.21	83.09 ± 14.70	78.54 ± 24.54
TNT	50.71 ± 26.73	57.51 ± 12.03	73.82 ± 21.84	75.67 ± 8.94
ViT	51.05 ± 26.16	62.28 ± 10.02	81.10 ± 13.39	79.92 ± 23.62
S-CNN	47.62 ± 22.74	94.24 ± 6.37	56.49 ± 16.68	85.55 ± 5.35
PiT	52.58 ± 22.79	70.94 ± 15.54	77.20 ± 13.08	80.47 ± 22.80
Hu et al.	49.73 ± 1.38	2.22 ± 4.62	7.13 ± 6.00	2.87 ± 4.53
Chen et al.	49.73 ± 1.38	66.53 ± 15.45	67.37 ± 37.45	87.28 ± 20.75

position, for the porcine dataset and improves slightly to the seventh place for the bovine dataset. We reiterate that transformers require large training datasets to perform well in similar tasks.

VII. CONCLUSION

We have conducted an extensive literature review of deep learning methods applied for hyperspectral image classification. The methods are divided into four groups based on architecture type: convolutional neural networks, recurrent neural networks, transformers, and graph neural networks. Within each group, papers are classified based on the information propagation axes, i.e., spatial, spectral, or spectral-spatial.

The automated classification of hyperspectral images of RF ablated atrial tissue has been unexplored until now

due to the unavailability of objective ground truth labels. We generate multiple sets of reference ROIs (nine ablated and nine unablated rectangular regions) for each image to enable supervised learning in this context. We apply 45 diverse classification algorithms on eleven porcine and bovine pre-clinical ablated atrial tissue HSI cubes.

The results of quantitative evaluation on sets of ROIs indicate that graph neural networks perform the best, accompanied by a linear unmixing algorithm [92], [93] implementation in the Nuance commercial software system. Moreover, the results show that most of the top-performing algorithms are trained on spatial dimensions.

Additional insights are acquired through the analysis of a comparative qualitative assessment of the eight top-performing algorithms. Seventeen participants are requested to rate RGB visualizations constructed from the classification

TABLE 6. Performance of all algorithms per datacube on the bovine dataset, ranked by overall OA scores. Per algorithm and per datacube, the OA average across the nine runs is reported, along with the standard deviation. A horizontal line separates the top ten algorithms from the rest. Row coloring is in accordance with the taxonomy in Fig. 1.

Model Name	bov1 OA (%)	bov2 OA (%)	bov3 OA (%)	bov4 OA (%)	bov5.1 OA (%)	bov5.2 OA (%)	bov5.3 OA (%)
GiGCN	96.13 ± 12.85	100.00 ± 0.00	96.92 ± 10.22	100.00 ± 0.00	93.18 ± 16.73	88.64 ± 19.69	98.01 ± 6.59
CEGCN	94.88 ± 16.97	100.00 ± 0.00	100.00 ± 0.00	99.39 ± 2.02	79.18 ± 25.55	97.87 ± 6.50	100.00 ± 0.00
Nuance LU	81.18 ± 6.21	73.42 ± 8.22	83.01 ± 10.71	95.72 ± 3.42	80.63 ± 10.32	89.92 ± 5.66	99.53 ± 0.56
HybridSN	85.05 ± 7.79	61.36 ± 10.03	96.32 ± 8.18	70.59 ± 18.31	73.12 ± 21.30	77.51 ± 16.59	95.94 ± 7.92
Sellars et al.	72.64 ± 14.57	72.20 ± 18.15	98.19 ± 1.17	71.68 ± 15.38	77.66 ± 11.00	63.31 ± 20.52	80.96 ± 9.94
SS-ConvNeXt	79.17 ± 18.63	73.82 ± 9.69	97.10 ± 0.86	74.60 ± 18.62	69.62 ± 9.86	70.63 ± 17.56	69.39 ± 14.40
MLP	82.53 ± 13.19	47.99 ± 12.09	97.65 ± 1.04	80.32 ± 16.97	60.81 ± 15.29	73.26 ± 18.38	70.43 ± 15.33
LeViT	75.02 ± 19.32	54.70 ± 12.54	97.24 ± 1.32	71.81 ± 23.56	34.63 ± 24.09	60.51 ± 23.24	55.22 ± 19.26
WFCG	84.59 ± 19.74	52.95 ± 20.75	88.19 ± 11.34	68.91 ± 33.41	54.58 ± 17.97	62.69 ± 19.11	35.18 ± 26.69
iFormer	73.49 ± 21.99	58.36 ± 13.74	81.93 ± 22.37	65.84 ± 24.20	46.22 ± 12.43	49.63 ± 8.57	53.84 ± 23.09
CvT	75.13 ± 16.85	59.64 ± 11.36	96.46 ± 1.43	66.75 ± 25.20	46.43 ± 10.87	48.83 ± 11.43	54.40 ± 15.69
He et al.	67.16 ± 20.19	44.79 ± 12.07	97.71 ± 1.32	75.02 ± 12.94	60.80 ± 15.70	50.08 ± 8.68	53.90 ± 17.85
FullyContNet	72.49 ± 21.48	45.49 ± 11.77	99.44 ± 0.97	66.85 ± 14.04	61.39 ± 15.55	52.85 ± 10.50	48.01 ± 10.08
Liu et al.	66.80 ± 19.34	52.66 ± 6.89	97.71 ± 1.64	60.98 ± 17.95	42.05 ± 23.68	53.44 ± 16.55	51.82 ± 18.32
Lee et al.	67.34 ± 18.38	43.71 ± 10.31	97.22 ± 1.27	69.09 ± 17.27	60.61 ± 15.60	47.80 ± 9.98	51.37 ± 11.05
SVM	65.79 ± 20.93	46.52 ± 13.30	97.79 ± 1.26	61.83 ± 22.53	61.04 ± 15.57	52.83 ± 14.10	49.26 ± 12.17
RVT	71.73 ± 20.20	45.45 ± 9.81	92.81 ± 12.73	70.27 ± 17.48	62.32 ± 14.25	50.06 ± 12.43	44.46 ± 21.64
HIT	65.90 ± 19.28	49.42 ± 7.28	99.13 ± 0.95	63.98 ± 17.83	60.26 ± 16.17	53.12 ± 12.60	47.66 ± 8.26
ASSMN	69.84 ± 12.59	43.79 ± 11.57	93.58 ± 5.88	60.42 ± 20.16	56.51 ± 13.94	51.58 ± 12.16	48.64 ± 10.66
Hamida et al.	64.62 ± 17.38	46.96 ± 5.27	98.04 ± 1.41	66.93 ± 10.26	61.22 ± 15.30	51.27 ± 10.64	49.97 ± 14.05
SpectralFormer	73.62 ± 19.77	43.96 ± 13.05	97.44 ± 1.17	56.95 ± 19.20	61.30 ± 15.23	48.16 ± 9.53	48.85 ± 11.53
SGD	71.19 ± 21.41	46.99 ± 12.81	97.58 ± 1.46	60.76 ± 18.76	45.69 ± 13.04	45.93 ± 10.41	48.53 ± 11.41
conv3d	64.39 ± 20.56	49.05 ± 5.43	97.90 ± 1.63	57.70 ± 18.18	45.15 ± 12.61	51.10 ± 9.51	49.05 ± 10.91
Chen et al.	48.99 ± 5.21	47.16 ± 9.39	70.04 ± 15.35	52.90 ± 2.68	65.86 ± 21.44	86.53 ± 1.47	50.77 ± 28.01
Mou et al.	65.66 ± 20.15	45.67 ± 9.90	97.53 ± 1.50	60.65 ± 20.18	46.48 ± 12.09	47.70 ± 10.34	49.76 ± 10.49
Hu et al.	48.99 ± 5.21	47.16 ± 9.39	70.04 ± 15.35	52.24 ± 3.12	65.86 ± 21.44	87.01 ± 1.31	50.77 ± 28.01
KNN	64.16 ± 19.51	42.91 ± 10.47	97.69 ± 1.32	58.72 ± 18.01	61.11 ± 15.42	49.05 ± 8.75	50.74 ± 15.81
ViP-P	65.50 ± 20.62	50.46 ± 10.01	97.47 ± 1.67	60.84 ± 18.44	44.20 ± 11.88	47.43 ± 9.23	49.96 ± 17.77
ViT	58.83 ± 15.58	46.09 ± 8.97	95.16 ± 5.18	61.50 ± 16.95	61.06 ± 15.59	50.25 ± 12.03	51.56 ± 14.76
TNT	60.32 ± 14.91	48.23 ± 6.05	97.17 ± 0.95	56.27 ± 16.64	62.28 ± 14.63	52.83 ± 12.08	48.55 ± 10.90
ViT	68.34 ± 18.98	45.76 ± 8.60	96.76 ± 1.81	58.69 ± 15.70	59.59 ± 16.99	45.60 ± 12.60	52.75 ± 9.36
T2T-ViT	61.52 ± 13.27	47.94 ± 9.41	80.08 ± 24.14	54.10 ± 15.75	61.45 ± 15.16	48.71 ± 16.95	45.15 ± 17.40
CrossViT	58.75 ± 17.28	45.92 ± 8.02	97.07 ± 1.04	59.01 ± 16.45	61.40 ± 15.00	51.28 ± 9.95	47.26 ± 11.08
DeepViT	58.31 ± 15.26	44.16 ± 10.14	97.99 ± 1.51	57.38 ± 16.15	62.00 ± 14.81	48.55 ± 10.20	50.32 ± 14.16
LocalViT	66.09 ± 20.54	43.65 ± 9.35	97.29 ± 1.36	56.79 ± 16.53	61.57 ± 15.49	50.88 ± 9.04	47.63 ± 10.40
Li et al.	58.94 ± 17.75	42.36 ± 10.57	97.80 ± 1.39	61.95 ± 12.70	60.80 ± 15.68	50.53 ± 9.38	50.37 ± 14.96
Wave-ViT	63.93 ± 18.78	46.06 ± 8.73	97.45 ± 1.51	59.35 ± 16.35	44.46 ± 12.00	47.18 ± 9.42	50.49 ± 17.67
Luo et al.	59.51 ± 7.32	45.11 ± 7.93	98.18 ± 0.94	57.76 ± 15.84	60.87 ± 15.57	51.27 ± 10.30	48.98 ± 11.96
Inception 3D	66.50 ± 18.68	46.55 ± 9.78	97.33 ± 1.38	60.95 ± 12.30	41.74 ± 10.91	52.52 ± 14.35	46.75 ± 8.80
CaiT	59.39 ± 15.37	45.24 ± 8.12	99.06 ± 1.37	56.86 ± 15.71	62.43 ± 14.14	46.59 ± 10.17	52.42 ± 9.24
Yang	65.47 ± 20.12	49.06 ± 9.38	93.60 ± 5.86	57.19 ± 17.72	45.60 ± 12.99	46.71 ± 9.91	44.69 ± 6.24
R-CNN	62.85 ± 18.11	49.21 ± 12.66	97.08 ± 2.03	59.90 ± 21.09	38.79 ± 22.86	48.60 ± 8.61	45.46 ± 6.46
Inception 2D	64.90 ± 17.24	45.71 ± 13.07	94.86 ± 5.78	55.03 ± 16.90	32.76 ± 25.14	47.95 ± 11.75	45.51 ± 8.22
PiT	57.59 ± 14.99	42.89 ± 11.86	86.89 ± 24.23	53.45 ± 12.70	60.58 ± 14.70	49.08 ± 8.53	46.03 ± 13.87
S-CNN	56.48 ± 28.99	47.50 ± 10.09	89.01 ± 29.64	37.42 ± 25.13	61.81 ± 14.39	17.62 ± 18.03	40.60 ± 19.17

outputs. The results on the more challenging bovine dataset show that Nuance linear unmixing is the first choice, followed by graph neural networks. One challenge observed for the visualization of graph-based methods is their reliance on superpixels and the consequent ‘pixelation’ in the visualized images. This explains the small relative decline of their scores in the qualitative experiment. CEGCN is observed as the method that consistently ranks among the top-performers in both experiments.

The findings of this paper are based on training and evaluating models using single image at a time. Future work includes exploring the applicability of these models across multiple images, both within and across species. Additionally, while the current training and testing were conducted using labeled rectangular regions, future efforts will focus on generating complete labels. Finally, extending

existing deep learning methods will be essential to enhance accuracy, particularly for bovine images.

APPENDIX A IMAGING SETUP

Experimental setup to acquire hyperspectral datasets from atrial tissue was described in details previously [90] and is shown schematically in Fig. 9. In brief, ablations were performed on freshly excised left atrial tissue from 5–6-month-old pigs (180–260 lb, mixed gender) with tissue collected immediately after surgical training at the Washington Institute of Surgical Education. Ablations were done using non-irrigated ablation catheter (EP Technologies) with tip temperatures ranging between 50 and 70° C. To acquire hypercubes, tissue samples were illuminated with a 365 nm UVA LED source (Mightex, Pleasanton, CA) while Nuance

FIGURE 11. Experimental setup with a 2560×1440 screen, designed to create a quiet and dark environment for participants, using a curtain to minimize external distractions and ensure optimal conditions for voting on deep learning model outputs.

FX multispectral imaging system comprised of a CCD camera and a liquid crystal tunable filter (PerkinElmer, Boston, MA) was used to capture images from 420 to 720 nm at 10 nm resolution.

APPENDIX B EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS PER DATACUBE

The OA scores of all algorithms per datacube are presented in Table 5 and Table 6 for the porcine and bovine datasets, respectively. In each table, the algorithms are ordered based on their overall OA scores. For individual datacubes, certain models achieve perfect accuracy (100%) on the sets of ROIs with a standard deviation of zero. On the bovine dataset, these top-performing algorithms are the GNN-based GiGCN and CEGCN. Instead, for the porcine dataset, simpler models like Nuance LU and MLP reach 100% accuracy on individual datacubes. This trend suggests that for data with simpler structures, simpler algorithms can achieve very high accuracy. In contrast, for more complex data, only sophisticated architectures can deliver the highest scores. Although complex models do not always score highest on simpler tasks, they nonetheless maintain strong overall performance across both datasets.

APPENDIX C VISUALIZATION PROCEDURE FOR DL RESULTS

Since binary segmentation masks do not reflect any measurable extent of RF ablation damage to tissue, in experimental settings where subjective evaluation of results is involved,

we generate alternative visualizations of results. This section describes the procedure for generating an interpretable RGB visualization of DL prediction results on the porcine and bovine HSI data. To give the rater information about the input HSI and the model output, we combine both of these together.

In order to generate a greyscale 2D image per HSI, per pixel, we sum the intensities across the spectral bands and normalize the image using min–max normalization.

Per model output, represented as two logits for the ablated and unablated tissue, histogram equalization is applied, followed by min–max normalization. These normalized logits are mapped to an RGB image, where the red and green channels are assigned to ablated and unablated logits, respectively, and the blue channel is set to zero.

To combine these two images, the RGB representation of the model output is converted to the HSV color space, and the value channel is replaced with the greyscale representation of the input HSI. The modified HSV image is then transformed back to the RGB color space. The blue channel in the final visualization image is reset to zero intensity once more to emphasize green and red hues for the ablated and unablated regions.

Post-processing of the final images involves adjustments to brightness, sharpness, contrast, and color saturation for improved visualization. The image is first smoothed using a `ImageFilter.SMOOTH_MORE` filter from the Python Pillow library to reduce noise. Brightness is reduced by 20%, sharpness is increased by a factor of 5, contrast is enhanced by 65%, and color saturation is boosted by 50%. These adjustments ensure clearer differentiation and a more vivid representation of the ablated and unablated regions, optimizing the clarity and interpretability of the final image. All parameters were set based on visual assessment of a few samples.

Figure 10 illustrates the visualization results for 10 data cubes, including 3 porcine and 7 bovine samples. The visualizations for the remaining porcine sample (porcine2) are given in Fig. 6.

APPENDIX D SETTING FOR QUALITATIVE EXPERIMENT PARTICIPATION

During the qualitative experiment, participants individually completed two separate sessions: one for porcine data and another for bovine data. The evaluations were conducted in a quiet, dark room with curtains, as shown in Fig. 11, to minimize external distractions and ensure optimal conditions for assessing algorithm performance. The session was displayed on a 2560×1440 screen, and participants were not restricted by time.

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